

Gender Inequality on the Organization Structure, Processes and Practices in the Public Service

Author Details: Elias Odula Barasa

Lecturer, Lower Kabete, Nairobi, Kenya, Kenya school of Government

Email:elias.odula@ksg.ac.ke

Abstract

Globally, gender inequality in organizations is a complex phenomenon seen in organizational structures, processes, and practices. Gender inequality has a negative impact on employers, employees, and human capital investment. Out of 153 nations, Kenya ranks 109 on the Global Gender Gap index 2020, representing a drop of 33 positions compared to that reported in 2018. Kenya sits at position 20, lagging behind fellow East African nations Rwanda, Uganda, Tanzania, and Ethiopia. Gender artificial barriers prevent women from advancing within their jobs or receiving promotions in Kenya's workplace. These barriers exist despite the achievements or qualifications of the women. The inequality effects of these barriers are more prevalent within higher levels of organizational structure, with fewer women occupying positions at those levels. This study explored the effects of gender inequality on the organization structure, processes and practices in the public service. Four specific objectives guided this study; to determine the effect of gender inequalities on the hiring process of the public service, to examine the relationship between gender inequalities and training, to examine gender inequalities in relation to promotions and to propose strategies to address gender inequalities towards improved performance within the public service. The independent variable was gender inequality, and dependent variables; hiring, promotion and training. Using simple random sampling and the Yamane formula, 55 respondents working at the public service and attending the SMC 378 cohort were identified from the Kenya School of Government. The independent variable was gender inequality and dependent variables; hiring, promotion and training. Data was collected by administering questionnaires and analysed using the descriptive statistics to draw important inferences. Findings indicated the existence of gender inequalities in hiring, promotion, and training opportunities. The human resource policy, bias, and unnecessary delays for promotions were also other factors that precipitated lack of promotions and training opportunities in the organization. In addition, ethnicity was an essential concern when it came to hiring. Organizations in the public service should offer equal opportunities for all their employees.

Key words: Gender Inequality, Organization Structure, Processes, Practices, Public Service

INTRODUCTION

Gender inequality is a concept used to describe the unequal behaviors, attitudes, and perceptions that individuals are subjected to according to their gender. Its origins are differences in gender roles (Sevgi et al., 2022).

Despite considerable progress in recent decades, gender inequality in many dimensions of well-being remains pervasive in many developing countries (Boris Branisa, 2013)

The current global labour force participation rate for women is just under 47%. For men, it is 72%. That is a difference of 25 per cent, with some regions facing a gap of more than 50 per cent (International Labour Organization, 2022).

The workplace has sometimes been referred to as an inhospitable place for women due to the multiple forms of gender inequalities present. Finding a job is much more challenging for women than for men. Moreover, employed women tend to work in low-quality jobs in vulnerable conditions, and there is a slight improvement to change the situation (International Labour Organization, 2022; Maggie, 2021).

Africa, 70 per cent of women are excluded financially. The continent has a US\$42 billion financing gap between men and women. Closing the gender gap for women and girls in all spheres of life is urgent globally, particularly in Africa, with girls at risk of being left behind (Victoria, 2019).

Kenya, twelve years after the promulgation of the 2010 constitution-which forbids gender discrimination, women are still receiving unequal treatment. Additionally, out of 153 nations, Kenya ranks 109 on the Global Gender Gap index 2020, representing a drop of 33 positions compared to that reported in 2018. Kenya sits at position 20, lagging behind fellow East African nations Rwanda, Uganda, Tanzania, and Ethiopia (UNICEF Global Gender Gap Report, 2020; Stella and Naima, 2018).

Given the highlighted situation, this paper evaluates the effects of gender inequalities on the organizational structure of the Public Service with a focus on the SMC 378/2022 cohort at the Kenya School of Government (KSG).

Statement of the Problem

Workplace discrimination contributes to women's lower socioeconomic status. Significantly, such discrimination against women largely can be attributed to human resources policies and human resources-related decision-making. Furthermore, when employees interact with organizational decision-makers during human resources practices or are told the outcomes of human resources-related decisions, they may experience personal discrimination in sexist comments. Both the objective disadvantages of lower pay, status and opportunities at work and the subjective experiences of being stigmatized affect women's psychological and physical stress, mental and physical health

Organizational practices and processes can contribute to gender inequality. Hiring determines who gets what position. Once employed, staff are subjected to training and promotion practices that determine mobility upward and contribute to performance. Gender inequality, more so at the management level, contributes to poor performance of the Public Service

The government of Kenya has instituted various strategies to improve service delivery by respective government departments and ministries to contribute towards the achievement of Kenya's Vision 2030. However, there has been limited progress in performance.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to assess the effects of gender inequalities on organizational structure, processes and practices in the public service

The specific objectives were;

- i. To determine the effect of gender inequalities on the hiring process of public servants.
- ii. To examine gender inequalities in relation to the promotion of public servants.
- iii. To examine the relationship between gender inequalities and training of public servants.
- iv. To propose strategies to address gender inequalities towards improved performance within the public service?

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework that guided this study consists of elements of radical feminism theory which focuses on the theory of patriarchy as a system of power that organizes society into a complex of relationships producing what radical feminists claim is male supremacy that oppresses women. Radical feminists locate the root cause of women's oppression in patriarchal gender relations, as opposed to legal systems. With male

supremacy in Kenyan society, women are oppressed and feel like victims. This victimization of women is brought about by the way the Kenyan society is patriarchal; thus, it works in favor of men.

This framework explored how gender inequality affects an organization's hiring, promotions, and training processes.

The basis of the illustration below is the idea that gender inequality in an organization affects the process of hiring, promotion and training. Therefore it is expected that gender inequality could affect the organization structure, processes and practices.

Figure 1.1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Odula (2022)

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Feminist Theory

The theory of feminism underscores the importance of economic, social, and political structures in shaping human society (Turner & Maschi, 2015). At the core of the theory is the belief that the inferiority delegated to women emanates from inequalities in society. It states that the personal statuses of women in society are shaped by power relations in political, social, and economic aspects (Turner & Maschi, 2015).

The theory requires the society to provide equal access to the three forms of power to all women and calls for the acknowledgement of gender when examining the issues of power, domination, and oppression in society (Jordan, 2010). The theory has been applied by social workers, educators, and activists to show women various ways they are oppressed and dominated, such as discrimination based on gender and objectification. In line with the theory, activists encourage women to participate actively in pushing for changes in the society in the belief society change is a guarantee for ending oppression and domination for women as well as to develop self-esteem and self-efficacy in women (Turner & Maschi, 2015; Jordan, Campbell, & Follingstad, 2010).

The feminist theory assumes that gender is a social construct, the basis on which the idea of 'unfairness' is founded. Furthermore, the theory implies that social interactions yield gender, so addressing gender-related issues has to begin with tackling the social interactions. However, according to Grosz (2010), Ferber and Nelson (2009), gender is a natural construct, inherently resulting in traditional femininity and masculinity. This implies that gender problems are part of natural selection with no particular solution. The theory has also been criticized for failing to acknowledge modern society's strides towards gender equality. Grosz (2010) believes that the theory is undermined because its practitioners add their biases to the theory.

Nonetheless, the feminist theory was considered vital for this study. The theory helped form the basis for gender inequality by highlighting the concept's foundational issues, such as domination and oppression.

Gender Inequality and the Hiring Process

Stamarski and Hing (2015) explored gender inequalities in the workplace, organizational structures, processes, practices and decision makers' sexism. The study concluded that human resource policies that are inherently biased against a group of people, regardless of their job-related knowledge, skills, abilities, and performance, can be termed institutional discrimination. Institutional discrimination against women can occur in each type of H.R. policy, from recruiting and selecting an individual into an organization through their role assignments, training, pay, performance evaluations, promotion, and termination. For instance, if women are under-represented in a particular educational program or a particular job type and those credentials or previous job experience must be considered for selection, women are being systematically and perhaps not intentionally discriminated against.

Fernandez and Fernandez (2016) found out that gender differences tend to play out at the start of the hiring process and are driven both by supply-side and demand-side actors. Once considered for a position, women are no less likely than men to be hired though they are slightly less likely to be interviewed by the search firm

Carnahan and Greenwood (2018) explored whether managers' beliefs and attitudes influence gender inequality among their subordinates. They analyze novel microdata from the U.S. legal industry from 2007 to 2012 and found that large law offices whose partners are more liberal hire a larger percentage of female associates, that more-liberal partners are more likely to select female associates to be members of their client teams, and that associates whose supervising partners are more liberal have greater gender parity in promotion rates.

Organizations and H.R. policies have encouraged a culture of gender inequality, where one gender is seen as low in terms of performance in comparison to the other gender. In this case, Male candidates tend to be favoured at the hiring stage; they get opportunities for job interviews while female job applicants are not accorded similar opportunities.

For example, in a recent study, male and female biology, chemistry, and physics professors rated an undergraduate science student for a laboratory manager position (Moss-Racusin et al., 2012). The male applicant was rated as significantly more competent and hireable, offered a higher starting salary (about \$4000), and offered more career mentoring than the female applicant was. In summary, women face a distinct disadvantage when considered for male-typed jobs.

Where women are considered for job interviews, the Hiring managers are biased against a female applicant who seems assertive, more confident or more self-aware. H.R. policies and hiring managers like less assertive female candidates. As a result, some women are more likely to be discriminated against in selection and performance evaluation decisions. Specifically, agentic women, who are assertive, are rated as less likeable and less hireable than comparable agentic male applicants. In most Organizations, women are associated with lower status, and men with higher status, women experience backlash for pursuing high-status roles in leadership in the workplace (Rudman et al., 2012). The stereotypes are associated with individuals, and employers discriminate against applicants with the 'wrong' gender (Bobbitt-Zeher, 2011).

Pregnant women are never spared this form of discrimination. They are viewed as less productive, slow and most likely would be more absent through the period of Pregnancy; there is evidence of discrimination against pregnant women when they apply for jobs (Morgan et al., 2013).

Gender Inequality and promotion in the workplace

Worldwide, most countries recognize equal rights between men and women. Many have produced regulations intended to fight discrimination and programs granting women access to health, education, and economic rights such as land ownership. However, the fact remains that women have fewer opportunities than men to benefit from economic development, with lower participation in the labour force. Even in the most advanced countries, their wages average 73 per cent of men's (Castro, 2010).

While women's education levels have increased globally and educated women now earn more than their uneducated peers, gender gaps in labour-market participation and wage levels persist. As a result, women continue to be underrepresented in formal and higher value-added employment (IFC, 2013).

Undoubtedly, women are a more significant part of society's social and spiritual capital. This immense capital plays a vital role in their country's development, both domestic and social functions. Unfortunately, however, women are subject to a tremendous disadvantage for gender in their careers (Firooz and Joshi, 2020).

Maggie Wooll (2021), states that in advanced states like America and Europe, for every 100 men promoted to manager, only 86 women are promoted. This problem is compounded at higher levels of leadership: fewer women managers means there are fewer candidates to promote to heads of department, directors, and C-suite positions, too. Moreover, 62 per cent of C-suite roles are held by white men, compared with 20% taken up by white women (greater than the 13% occupied by men of colour) and a mere 4% by women of colour.

Furthermore, managers frequently identify candidates for employment opportunities by relying on their networks for recommendations, which usually consists of people of the same gender, race, identity. This further perpetuates the imbalance in representation (Maggie Wooll, 2021).

Discrimination can be present within HR policies to determine employee selection, performance evaluations, and promotions. These policies can significantly affect women's careers (Cailin and Leanne, 2015).

Institutional discrimination against women also occurs in performance evaluations used to determine organizational rewards, opportunities like promotion and role assignments, and punishments. Gender discrimination can be formalized into H.R. policy if criteria used by organizational decision-makers to evaluate job performance systematically favour men over women. For instance, "face time" is a key performance metric that rewards employees at the office more than those who are not. Given that women are still the primary caregivers (Fuegen et al., 2011), women use flexible work arrangements more often than men and, consequently, face career penalties because they score lower on face time. Thus, biased criteria in performance evaluation policies can contribute to gender discrimination.

H.R. policies surrounding promotions and opportunities for advancement are another area of concern. In organizations with more formal job ladders that are used to dictate and constrain workers' promotion opportunities, women are less likely to advance. This occurs because job ladders tend to be divided by gender. As such, gender job segregation seen at entry-level positions will be strengthened as employees move up their specific ladder with no opportunity to cross into other lines of advancement. Thus, women will lack particular job experiences that are not available within their particular job ladders, making them unqualified for promotion (De Pater et al., 2010).

According to (IFC, 2013), economic growth is more robust and sustainable when women and men participate fully in the labour market. Better jobs for women, employment that leads to higher wages and greater decision-making. While gender equity in the workplace is generally accepted, discriminatory practices persist in many organizations despite regulations to the contrary. Yet despite the persuasive evidence that gender equality has a transformative effect on productivity and growth, women's full economic and productive potential remains unrealized in many parts of the world (IFC, 2013 and Castro, 2010).

Gender Inequality in relation to training

Women are also likely to receive fewer opportunities at work than men, resulting in their under-representation at higher levels of management and leadership within organizations. Managers give women fewer challenging roles and fewer training opportunities than men (King et al., 2012; Glick, 2013). For instance, female managers and midlevel workers (De Pater et al., 2010) have less access to high-level responsibilities and challenges that are precursors to promotion. Further, men are more likely to be given vital leadership assignments in male-dominated and female-dominated fields (De Pater et al., 2010).

In a study published in the American Sociological Review, researchers considered whether high school graduates in blue-collar communities those in the top 25 percentile in the research sample for the number of blue-collar labourers benefit from an emphasis on vocational training in high school. The study showed that blue-collar training without a strong college preparatory curriculum leads to blue-collar job opportunities for men but penalizes women, who end up earning 78 cents to a man's dollar.

Formal on the job training (FOJT) can have a positive impact on promotion opportunities. However, first, women are less likely than men to participate in FOJT. Second, once women get more remunerative training – such as general Training and Training that increases promotion opportunities – they are not rewarded for their new skills to the same extent as men are. Third, women are more likely to participate in industry-specific training than those who receive training. In contrast, men are more likely to participate in general training, which increases promotion opportunities.

RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

Research design refers to the overall strategy used to integrate the different components of the study coherently and logically, thereby ensuring the research problem is effectively addressed. It constitutes the blueprint for collecting, measuring, and analyzing data. Descriptive design is appropriate when the research aims at identifying the characteristics, frequencies and categories of variables.

This study was conducted through descriptive research design to explore the effects of gender inequality as the independent variable on Hiring, Promotion and Training as the dependent variables. This design was suitable due to the categorical nature of the variables in this study. Data was collected by administering questionnaires, and the sample size was determined using simple random sampling. Data was analyzed using the Pearson Chi-Square test.

Study research comprised of 73 respondents with the sample was drawn through simple random sampling. This is a sampling technique in which a subset of individuals are chosen randomly and with the same probability of being selected (Attia, Moosavi, & Sandu, 2018). This technique was selected due to ease of use and accuracy of representation.

The sample size for the study was determined using the Yamane formula with a 5 per cent level of precision and a 95 per cent confidence level (Sarmah, Hazarika, & Choudhury, 2013), as indicated below.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)}$$

Where N = population of 65, e = level of precision, of 0.05 and n = sample size giving

$$n = \frac{65}{1 + 65(0.05^2)}$$

$$n = \frac{65}{1 + 65 * 0.05 * 0.05}$$

$$n = \frac{65}{1 + 65 * 0.0025}$$

The measurement of gender inequality in the public service was in three dimensions; staff hiring, promotion and training. The analysis included stratifying by demographics and calculating average frequencies. The analysis

for the effects of gender inequality in the public service was tabulated, and a summary score for every variable was calculated. The descriptive statistics frequencies will be used to draw important inference due to the categorical nature of the variables. SPSS version 25 was the statistical software that was used to analyze the data.

RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Characteristics

The demographic characteristic of the respondents is summarized in table 4.2.1, this attribute of the respondents' shows the effect of Gender Inequality on the Organization Structure, Processes and Practices in the Public Service. A total of 55 respondents were involved in the study resulting in a 100% response rate. The demographic factors assessed in this study included Gender, Age, Education and organization.

Table 4.2.1 shows the demographic profiles of the sampled respondents, the results indicated that 27 out of 55 respondents were male and 28 were female. Respondents between the ages of 25-34 and 35-44 were evenly distributed between both genders at 23 (41%), respectively, while the respondents above 55 years were the least (5.5%). 26 out of 55 respondents had an undergraduate degree with male being the majority (14) and female (12). 21 out of 55 had masters and PhD degrees out of which men were 11 and female were only 10.

Comparatively more women had college and tertiary qualification at 6 against 2 men. The implication of this is that it will limit most women when being promoted to higher ranks hence affecting their performance because of least qualification as compared to men. Most female worked at the county government and parastatal while more men worked with national government.

Table 4.2.1: Demographic profiles of the respondents in relation to gender

	AGE BRACKET OF THE RESPONDENT				Total
	25-34	35-44	45-55	ABOVE	
MALE	11	11	4	1	27
FEMALE	12	12	2	2	28
	HIGHEST LEVEL OF EDUCATION			Total	
	COLLEGE/TERTIARY	UNDERGRADUATE DEGREE	DEGREE MASTERS/PHD		
MALE	2	14	11	27	
FEMALE	6	12	10	28	
	ORGANIZATION RESPONDENTS WORK			Total	
	NATIONAL GOVERNMENT	COUNTY GOVERNMENT	PARASTATAL		
MALE	10	11	6	27	
FEMALE	4	15	9	28	
	ENTRY CADRE IN THE ORGANIZATION				Total
	JUNIOR STAFF	SUPERVISOR	MID-LEVEL MANAGER	SENIOR MANAGER	
MALE	10	12	4	1	27
FEMALE	10	7	10	1	28

Source: Odula (2022)

The Effect of Gender Inequalities on The Hiring Process of Public Servants.

The study examined the effect of gender inequality on the hiring process. The period spent in organization and factors influencing hiring in the organization were assessed. The summary of responses was as shown below.

What influenced your hiring?

The results demonstrated that both men and women believed that their qualification influenced their hiring to the organization which is the same across different levels of management. The results also revealed that respondents with high level of academic qualification that is post graduate degree occupied the position of senior manager and mid-level manager. On the period spent in the organization junior staff had spent less than 3

years while supervisors, mid-level managers and senior managers had spent time between 3-6 years, 6-9 years and above 9 years. This evaluation revealed that some good progress had been made by the organizations to address the gender inequality. Both men and women perceived that their qualification was the consideration for them being hired and not gender as shown in table 4.2 below;

Table 4.2: frequency distribution for the period spent in organization and factors that influence hiring.

Variable	Category	Men (n)	Percentage (%)	Female (n)	Percentage (%)	Total (M&F)	Percentage (%)
Period Spent in Current Organization	<3 Years	1	1.8	4	7.3	5	9.1
	3-6 Years	10	18.2	10	18.2	20	36.4
	6-9 Years	7	12.7	7	12.7	14	25.4
	>9 Years	9	16.4	7	12.7	16	29.1
	Total	27	49.1	28	50.9	55	100.0
Factors Influences Hiring	Qualification	16	29.1	16	29.1	32	58.2
	Gender	4	7.2	4	7.2	8	14.4
	Ethnicity	6	11.0	7	12.8	13	23.8
	Others	1	1.8	1	1.8	2	3.6
	Total	27	49.1	28	50.9	55	100.0

Source: Odula (2022)

Inferential analysis and Discussion of Results

Gender Inequalities in Relation to the Promotion of Public Servants.

Discrimination can be present within HR policies to determine employee selection, performance evaluations, and promotions (Cailin and Leanne, 2015).

The results of this study revealed that 49% of the respondents got promoted in the last 3 years as shown in table 4.3 and strongly believed that they qualified for promotion. The findings indicated that more men got promoted as compared to women despite them having the requisite qualification. This demonstrated unfair treatment of women which in turn limits their achievements and interests to ascend to senior positions.

Generally, the results showed that there are other contributing factors which affect promotion in the public service which included: the highest level attained, public sector HR policy, bias and unnecessary delays for promotions. When the respondents were asked their opinions on how promotions were conducted in their organization and their satisfaction level, the survey revealed that most of the respondents (22) adopted a neutral response. At the same time, only 3 were highly satisfied with how their organizations conduct promotion as shown in table 4.5 below. The dissatisfied respondents indicated that, bias and favoritism was the key reason as shown in Table 4.5 below.

Table 4.3: Organizational Dimension; Respondents Promoted in the Last 3 Years

Variable	Category	Male		Female		Total	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Gender	Promoted	15	27.3	12	21.7	27	49.0
	Not promoted	12	21.9	16	29.1	28	51.0
Total		27		28		55	100

Source: Odula (2022)

Figure 1; Graphical percentage representation for the respondents promoted in the last three years

Source: Odula (2022)

Figure 2; Graphical representation for factors that necessitated promotion

Source: Odula (2022)

Table 4.4; Respondent's perceptions on factors that hampered their promotion

Frequency distribution					
variable	strongly disagree	Disagree	neutral	agree	strongly agree
Age	21	5	2	0	0
Gender	17	3	1	3	4
Education	23	3	1	0	1

Source: Odula (2022)

Table 4.5; Frequency Distributions for other Factors That Influence Promotion

Highest Attained Level	Inadequate Resources	Delays	Public Sector Hr Policy	Bias	Education Level
6	1	6	7	7	1
Satisfaction With how The Promotions are Conducted In The Organization					
Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neutral	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied	
3	7	22	17	6	
Reasons For Dissatisfaction With Promotions					
Promotions Based On Performance	Not On	Promotions Based On Affiliation	Bias / Favoritism	Delays	Being Overlooked
1		2	10	8	1
					Promotions Based On Lobbying
					1

Source: Odula (2022)

The Relationship Between Gender Inequalities and Training of Public Servants.

Women are also likely to receive fewer opportunities at work than men, resulting in their under-representation at higher levels of management and leadership within organizations (King et al., 2012; Glick, 2013). The survey revealed that most women who were junior staff got fewer opportunities of training than men despite their qualification hence hampering their promotion.

The findings also revealed that more men participated in training which led to increased promotion opportunities as compared to female. Out of the 44% who did not receive the training, majority were women who strongly disagreed that education level was a contributory factor to their lack of training as shown in Table 4.7 below. 35% of those who were not trained attributed bias/favoritism as the greatest factor that hindered them from receiving any training followed by COVID 19 pandemic (31%) while Job cadre, inadequate resources, and lack of opportunities ranked least as shown in figure 4 below. The results revealed a strong relationship between gender inequalities and training of the public servants, more males were likely to be considered as compared to females despite other considerations being constant. Respondents strongly agreed that training (34 out of 55) and promotion (40 out of the 55) are HR practices which immensely affect performance as shown in table 4.8. They indicated that these HR practices boost their morale and that they feel more motivated while discharging their duties, as shown in Figure 5 below;

Table 4.6: Organizational Dimension; Respondents Trained in the last 1 year

	Male	Female	Total
Variable Category	Frequency n=55		%
Trained	19	12	56
Not Trained	8	16	44
Total	27	28	100

Source: Odula (2022)

Figure 3; Graphical percentage representation for the respondents trained in the FY 2020/21

Source: Odula (2022)

Table 4.7; Respondent's perceptions as to why they did not receive training

Frequency Distributions					
Variable	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Gender	16	2	1	4	1
Age	22	1	1		
educational level	23			1	
job cadre	9	2	4	8	3

Source: Odula (2022)

Figure 4; Graphical percentage representation for other factors that influence Training

Source: Odula (2022)

Human Resource Practices and Performance

Table 4.8; Frequency Distribution for H.R. Practices that Affect Respondents Performance

Variable	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Training	0	0	2	19.0	34.0
Promotion	0	0	3	12.0	40.0

Source: Odula (2022)

Figure 5; Graphical representation of the effect of training and promotion on performance

Source: Odula (2022)

Strategies to Improve Performance within the Public Service?

Some of the strategies to improve performance in the public service are; focusing on strengthening capacity building, increasing training budget, prompt recognition and award upon appraisal and fair treatment to all employees.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

Summary of Main Findings

The study showed that there exists gender inequality in the public service in relation to training and promotion. The survey revealed that females are likely to get fewer opportunities of training than male despite their qualification hence hampering their promotion opportunities that may prevail as a reward.

The respondents strongly agreed that training and promotion are HR practices which immensely affect performance in their organizations. They indicated that these HR practices boost their morale and that they feel more motivated while discharging their duties.

Conclusions

This study has demonstrated that the issues of gender inequality significantly influence the processes of hiring, promotions and Training to a larger extent.

Recommendations

Public service should offer equal opportunities to all employees without gender discrimination. Such a practice will ensure sustained improvements in performance.

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